

The Influence of Supervision on Employee Performance at PT. Persada Technical Media

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to determine and analyze the influence of supervision on employee performance at PT. Persada Technique. This research was conducted using a causal associative quantitative approach. The sample used was all company employees, with a total of 61 people. The research results show that supervision has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This is shown by the T-count value of 3.193 which is greater than the T-table 11.818 > t table 1.67109, with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05. The regression coefficient shows that if supervision is increased by 1 unit, employee performance will increase by 1,709 units assuming other variables remain constant. Apart from that, the results of the determination test show an Adjusted R Square value of 0.698 or 69.80%, which indicates that supervision has a low influence on employee performance, while the remaining 30.20% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied. Thus, partially, supervision has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at PT. Persada technique. This identifies that, meaning, improvements in Supervision can contribute to improving employee performance.

Keywords: influence, supervision; employee performance

INTRODUCTION

In every company, supervision has a crucial role in ensuring that operations run according to established standards, ensuring compliance, efficiency and quality (Sukmawati & Susilo, 2023). However, implementing oversight is not always easy and often faces challenges, both in terms of resources, technology and internal policies. On the other hand, organizational performance is a vital aspect in maintaining a company's competitiveness. Good performance evaluation helps companies identify areas that need to be improved or optimized to achieve their business goals (Listiani, 2011).

This statement is supported by research results (Hendriani, 2020) which state that good leadership followed by good discipline will improve performance. This means that better supervision and commitment followed by high work discipline will improve performance.

PT. Media Teknik Persada is a company that provides products and services in the transformer business sector, whether repairing or refining transformer oil. Apart from that, this company also provides low and medium voltage electrical installation services. Based on the results of the author's observations through observations and interviews with several employees, information was obtained that first, the company has challenges in maintaining the effectiveness of the supervisory system implemented. Another thing is that there is a lack of adequate resources as well as gaps in policies or procedures, or lack of integration with technology. Second, organizational performance is still less than optimal due to various factors such as lack of operational efficiency, low productivity, or non-compliance

with relevant industry standards. Third, problems related to low levels of employee commitment.

According to (Afandi, 2018) employee performance is the work result that can be achieved by a person or group of people in a company in accordance with their respective authority and responsibilities in an effort to achieve organizational goals illegally, does not violate the law and does not conflict with morals and ethics.

To measure employee performance, this research refers to theory (Afandi, 2018) which is as follows:

1. Quantity of work output;
2. Quality of work results;
3. Efficiency in carrying out tasks;
4. Work discipline;
5. Initiative ;
6. Accuracy;
7. Leadership;
8. Honesty; And
9. Creativity.

To achieve maximum performance, many factors can influence it. This research is limited to supervision factors. According to (Handoko, 2013) supervision is the process by which organizational and management goals are achieved. This is concerned with ways of doing activities according to plan. Meanwhile, according to Brantas in (Wulandani, 2018) explains that Supervision is measuring and improving the implementation of subordinates' work, so that plans that have been made to achieve company goals can be implemented.

In this research, the definition of supervision refers to Siagian's theory (Susilawati et al., 2023) which states that it is a process of following the development of activities to ensure the progress of work, so that it can be completed perfectly as previously planned, by correcting several interconnected thoughts.

To measure supervision, this research refers to the indicators formulated by Handoko in (Susilawati et al., 2023) which are as follows:

1. Standard setting;
2. Work measurement;
3. Performance assessment;
4. corrective action

The aim of this research is to explore the extent to which the effectiveness of the company's supervisory system influences organizational performance. Through this research, it is hoped that factors that influence supervisory effectiveness and organizational performance can be identified, so that it can provide valuable insight for company management in improving supervisory systems and improving organizational performance. This research is expected to contribute to theoretical and practical understanding of supervisory management, organizational performance, and human resource development, at PT. Media Teknik Persada. The concept of this research is as depicted in the following conceptual framework image:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHOD

This type of research is casual associative quantitative research with the aim of analyzing the pattern of relationships between variables with the aim of finding out the influence between two independent variables (exogenous) on the dependent variable (endogenous) (Kuncooro, Munajad, 2013). This research was carried out at PT. Media Teknik Persada. This research was carried out from March to May 2024. According to (Sugiyono, 2018) population is a generalized area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by the researcher to be studied and then conclusions drawn. In this study the population used was the entire number of employees at PT. Media Teknik Persada with 67 employees with the following details:

Table 1. Population details at PT. Persada Engineering Media

No.	Division	Number of people)
1.	Electrical	47
2.	Transformation	10
3.	Marketing	6
4.	HRD and Finance	4
Amount		67

Source: PT. Persada Engineering Media

The sampling technique used in this research was a saturated sample. According to Sugiyono (2019) Saturated sampling is a sample selection technique if all members of the population are sampled, where the entire population in this study is sampled, namely 67 employees.

The data that will be used from this research is the data from the questionnaire distributed to respondents consisting of all employees in all divisions. The data analysis technique used in this research is a quantitative data analysis method using SPSS version 25.0.

Validity and reliability tests were carried out in order to test the quality of the research data. The validity test decision making criteria are as follows: If $r_{count} > r_{table}$, then the question item is valid. If $r_{count} < r_{table}$, then the question item is invalid. Meanwhile, the reliability test criteria are formulated if $r_{alpha} > r_{table}$ then the statement is reliable and if $r_{alpha} < r_{table}$ then the statement is not reliable.

The linear regression model was formulated in this research with the following formula:

$$Y = a + bX$$

Where :

Y = Employee Performance

X = Supervision

a = Constant

b = Regression coefficient

The t-test in this research was carried out to determine the significance of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable (Kuncooro, Munajad, 2013). According to (Kuncooro, Munajad, 2013) the determination test (R^2) is used to measure how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable. In other words, the coefficient of determination is used to assess the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable studied, namely supervision (X), on the dependent variable, namely employee performance (Y). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value ranges from zero to one ($0 < R^2 < 1$) which means, if $R^2 = 0$, then there is no influence between variable (X) and variable (Y). Conversely, if R^2 approaches 1, then the influence between variable (X) and variable (Y) becomes stronger. Testing of the coefficient of determination was carried out using SPSS version 25.0 software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Contents Results and Discussion

1. Research result

a) Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive Analysis This test is used to determine the minimum and maximum scores, the highest scores, rating scores and standard deviations for each variable. The results are as follows:

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
Supervision	61	2.00	3.00	5.00	4.3705	.49845	,248
Employee performance	61	1.90	3.10	5.00	4.3131	.45478	,207
Valid N (listwise)	61						

The table above shows that the measurement results show that respondents assess the supervision and performance of employees at PT. Media Teknik Persada is above average, with mean scores of 4.3705 and 4.3131 respectively on a scale of 1-5. The variation in respondents' assessments of these two variables is quite moderate, with almost the same standard deviation indicating that although there are individual differences in perception, the majority of respondents have quite positive views of these two variables.

b) Validity and Reliability Test Results

Validity Test Results

The validity test is used to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not. Validity testing carried out in this research was through the Corrected Item-Total Correlation test or better known as Person Correlation.

Table 3. Validity Test Results of Supervision Variables (X)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
X1	0.872 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X2	0.920 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X3	0.913 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X4	0.908 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above, it can be stated that the indicators on the gender variable have a correlation coefficient value of $> 0, 0.2521$ with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the supervision variable indicators are valid (Sugiyono, 2017).

Table 4. Validity Test Results for Employee Performance Variables (Y)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
Y.1	0.808 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.2	0.790 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.3	0.781 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.4	0.891 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.5	0.902 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.6	0.771 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.7	0.841 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.8	0.778 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.9	0.762 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above it can be stated that all indicators on the employee performance variable have a correlation coefficient value greater than 0.2787 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ so it can be concluded that the statements for the employee performance variable are valid (Sugiyono, 2016).

Reliability Test Results

According to (Ghozali, 2016) the reliability test aims to measure how reliable or reliable the questionnaire distributed to respondents is, which is useful as an instrument in this research. The reliability measurement method used in this research is by looking at the Cronbach Alpha (a) value. The questionnaire is declared reliable if the Cronbach Alpha (a) value is > 0.61 .

Table 5. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Supervision	0.923	4
Employee performance	0.935	9

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25.0

Based on table 5, it is known that the Cronbach Alpha (a) value of the supervision and employee performance variables is greater than 0.60. So it can be concluded that all indicators in the variable instrument are declared reliable or reliable so that they can proceed to research hypothesis testing

c) Quantitative Analysis

This analysis is intended to determine the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The test results are as follows:

Simple Linear Regression Analysis

This regression test is intended to determine changes in the dependent variable if the independent variable experiences changes. The test results are as follows:

Table 6. Simple Linear Regression Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	9,016	2,538		3,552	,001
Supervision	1,709	,145	,838	11,818	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee performance

Based on the test results in table 8, the regression equation $Y = 9.016 + 1.709X$ is obtained. This equation is explained as follows: 1) A constant of 9.016 means that if there is no supervision, then there is an employee performance of 9.016 points. The regression coefficient for supervision is 1.709, meaning that supervision influences an increase in employee performance by 1.709 for every 1 point increase.

Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination

To determine the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, a coefficient of determination analysis was carried out. The test results are as follows:

Table 7. Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.838a	,703	,698	2.24468	,703	139,670	1	59	,000

The test results in table 7 show that the Adjusted R Square value is 0.698 or 69.80%, which means that supervision has a moderate influence on employee performance, while the remaining 30.20% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

t Test Results (Hypothesis Test)

Hypothesis testing with the t test is used to determine whether or not there is an influence of the dependent variable on the independent variable with the following hypothesis formulation:

Ho: There is no influence of supervision on employee performance at PT. Media Teknik Persada

Ha: There is an influence of supervision on employee performance at PT. Media Teknik Persada

The following are the results of the hypothesis test as shown in the following table:

Table 8. Hypothesis Test Results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
		1	(Constant)	9,016		
	Supervision	1,709	,145	,838	11,818	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee performance

Based on the test results in table 8, the calculated t value is 11.818 > t table 1.67109, with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, thus it can be stated that Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted or that there is a positive and significant influence between supervision on employee performance at PT. Media Teknik Persada.

Contents of Discussion Results

From the results of data analysis, research findings showed that supervision had a positive and significant effect on employee performance. These findings are in line with research results from (Sari et al., 2018) and (Fachrunnisa, 2016) which state that supervision has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

The implications of these findings indicate that supervisory effectiveness plays an important role in improving employee performance. Therefore, management needs to strengthen the supervisory system by ensuring that leaders have good leadership skills, are able to provide clear direction, and are able to carry out constructive evaluation and feedback. In addition, supervisors must create a supportive work environment, where

employees feel valued and motivated to achieve the best results. By strengthening supervision, organizations can increase employee productivity and overall performance, thus contributing positively to achieving company goals and vision (Cahyati & Adelia, 2024).

CLOSING

Conclusion

From the results of the research data analysis and discussion described above, it can be concluded that:

1. Hypothesis test results show that supervision has a positive effect on employee performance. This can be seen from the T-count value of $11.818 > t$ table 1.67109 , with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This regression coefficient shows that if supervision is increased by 1 unit, the change in employee performance as seen from the Y value will increase by 1,709 units assuming other variables are considered constant. Thus, partially supervision has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at PT. Persada Engineering Media
2. Based on the results of the termination test, it shows that the Adjusted R Square value is 0.698 or 69.80%, which means that supervision has a moderate influence on employee performance, while the remaining 30.20% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

Suggestions and Acknowledgments

Based on the results of the discussion and conclusions of this research, several things can be suggested to PT. Persada Technical Media includes:

1. Management needs to develop special training programs for leaders and division heads to improve leadership skills, communication and the ability to provide constructive feedback. This training can include effective leadership techniques, strategies for resolving conflict, and methods for motivating employees. By improving the competency of supervisors, it is hoped that they can provide better guidance and support to employees, which will ultimately improve their performance.
2. Creating a work environment that is supportive and conducive for employees to develop is very important. Management must ensure that supervisors have the tools and resources necessary to perform their duties well, as well as create a work culture that values the contributions of each employee. Steps such as recognition and appreciation of employee achievements, opportunities for career development, and open communication between supervisors and employees can increase employee motivation and performance. Thus, PT. Media Teknik Persada can achieve its goals and vision more effectively.

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